

BIOLOGICAL BASIS OF FRUIT CROP PROCESSING AND METHODS OF PROPERTY

SALIEV SARDORBЕК ALISHEROVICH

Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnology

Professor of "Intensive vegetable, horticulture, viticulture and greenhouses"

KHOLIKOV RAVSHANBEK IKROMJON OGLI,

KHUSANOV BAHRIDDIN BAKHTIYORJON OGLI

Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnology

masters

ALIEV JAVOXIR KHABIBULLOX OGLI

Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnology

Student

Annotation. This thesis provides information on two methods of reproduction of fruit crops: sexual (from seed) and asexual (vegetative).

Keywords: fruit, berry-fruit, citrus crops, seeds, vegetative, hybrid, twig, root, graft, bud.

МЕВА ЭКИНЛАРИНИ КЎПАЙТИРИШНИНГ БИОЛОГИК АСОСЛАРИ ВА КЎПАЙТИРИШ УСУЛЛАРИ

САЛИЕВ САРДОРБЕК АЛИШЕРОВИЧ

Андижон қишлоқ хўжалиги ва агротехнологиялар институти

“Интенсив сабзавотчилик, боғдорчилик, узумчилик ва иссиқхона

хўжаликлари” кафедраси профессор- ўқитувчиси

ХОЛИҚОВ РАВШАНБЕК ИКРОМЖОН ЎҒЛИ,

ХУСАНОВ БАХРИДДИН БАХТИЁРЖОН ЎҒЛИ

Андижон қишлоқ хўжалиги ва агротехнологиялар институти

магистрантлари

АЛИЕВ ЖАВОХИР ХАБИБУЛЛОХ ЎҒЛИ

*Андижон қишлоқ хўжалиги ва агротехнологиялар институти
талабаси*

Аннотация. Мазкур тезисда мева экинларини кўпайтиришнинг икки усули яъни жинсий (уруғдан) ва жинссиз (вегетатив) йўл билан кўпайиши хабида маълумотлар келтирилган.

Калит сўзлар: мева, резавор-мева, цитрус экинлар, уруғ, вегетатив, дурагай, новда, илдиз, пайвандтаг, куртак.

БИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ПЕРЕРАБОТКИ ПЛОДОВЫХ КУЛЬТУР И СПОСОБЫ СОБСТВЕННОСТИ

САЛИЕВ САРДОРБЕК АЛИШЕРОВИЧ

*Андижанский институт сельского хозяйства и агротехнологий
Профессор кафедры «Интенсивное овощеводство, садоводство,
виноградарство и теплицы»*

**ХОЛИКОВ РАВШАНБЕК ИКРОМЖОН ОГЛИ,
ХУСАНОВ БАХРИДДИН БАХТИЕРДЖОН ОГЛИ**

*Андижанский институт сельского хозяйства и агротехнологий
мастера*

АЛИЕВ ДЖАВОКСИР ХАБИБУЛЛОХ ОГЛИ

*Андижанский институт сельского хозяйства и агротехнологий
ученик*

Аннотация. В диссертации представлены сведения о двух способах размножения плодовых культур: половом (из семян) и бесполом (вегетативном).

Ключевые слова: плодовые, ягодно-плодовые, цитрусовые культуры, семена, вегетативный, гибридный, побег, корень, привой, почка.

Ensuring the implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019 No PF-5853 "On approval of the Strategy of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030" It is planned to develop arable and fallow lands, increase the planting of export-oriented agricultural crops on cotton and grain fields, as well as to make effective use of the potential of orchards, vineyards and greenhouses. The climate of Uzbekistan is sharply continental, and its sharp variability is inextricably linked with the influence of geographical location, relief, intensity of solar radiation, atmospheric circulation.

The growth, development and yield of fruit crops depend in many ways on environmental factors. In particular, climatic and soil factors have a major impact on the growth and development of fruit crops. This requirement varies throughout the year (spring, summer, autumn, winter) at different stages of plant age (youth, yield and aging), growth and dormancy phases. It is possible to alleviate unfavorable conditions and create optimal conditions for their growth and yield through the planting of fruit seedlings and agro-technical measures for their care.

In horticulture, fruit and berry and citrus crops are propagated in two ways: sexually (from seed) and asexually (vegetatively). The method of sexual reproduction is used to create varieties of fruit and berry-fruit and citrus crops and to grow grafts. Many fruit and berry-bearing plants are pollinated from the outside and produce seeds. These seeds retain the characteristics of two individuals (parents), and plants grown from such plants become hybrids. In practice, vegetative propagation of fruit and berry and citrus crops is widely used. Vegetative propagation is based on the ability of a certain part of a plant to regenerate from a viable part - a branch, root, leaf and even a piece of tissue. In vegetative propagation, the plant is kept relatively pure, to which the traits and characteristics of the mother plant are transferred. When sexually propagated, a hybrid with both maternal and paternal, and sometimes the traits of the most ancient ancestors is obtained. There

are many methods of vegetative propagation of fruit and berry and citrus crops, which can be divided into the following groups:

- a) dividing the stems and roots into parts (gajak) by rooting the tubers, dividing the bushes, planting cuttings and root cuttings, pruning, etc ;
- b) grafting (transplantation).

Most fruit and citrus crops are propagated by grafting. In this case, one plant (cultivar) in the form of cuttings or buds (graft) is grafted to another plant (graft) that grows from seed in the soil. In this case, the cultivated plant grows on the root of another plant (grafttag). Plants that have sprouted from a stalk or a piece of root will have their own root. There are several methods of grafting: bud or eye grafting (is the main method of propagating fruit plants); There are more than 150 methods in total, such as fitting welding, installation in the form of a saddle into the shell, cut welding, grain welding, semi-grain welding, side cut welding, double grafting (ablaktirovka), etc.

ФЙДАЛАНИЛГАН АДАБИЁТЛАР

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Қишлоқ хўжалиги вазирлиги ҳамда “Agrobank” ҳамкорлигида тайёрланган “100 та китоб”дан иборат тўплами.
2. Афанасьев О.К. Интенсивные сады на слаборослых подвоях. Ташкент. 1978.
3. Останақулов Т.И., Нарзиева С., Ғуломов Б.Х. Мевачилик асослари. Тошкент. 2013.
4. Ражаметов Ш., Нормуратов И., Адиллов Х., Жанақова Д., Намазов И. Мева, резавор мева ва ток кўчатларини ташкил этиш. Тошкент. 2018.
5. Рибаклов А.А., Остроухова С.В. Ўзбекистон мевачилиги. Тошкент “Ўқитувчи”. 1981.
6. Xatamova, X. K., Yuldasheva, K. T., Soliyeva, M. B., Kimsanova, X. A., & Juraboyeva, S. M. (2021). Methods of preserving subtropical fruits. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR), 10(1), 109-115.

7. Асронов, Э. К., Салиева, М. Б., Салиев, С. А., & Давлатов, Х. Р. (2018). ХРАНЕНИЕ ПЛОДООВОЩНОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ. In Северный морской путь, водные и сухопутные транспортные коридоры как основа развития Сибири и Арктики в XXI веке (pp. 264-266).
8. Z.T.Bo'stanov, S.A.Saliyev, X.N.Berdaliyev "Andijon sharoitida boshli va bargli salatning qish oldidan ekish va ularni morfo-biologik baholash" Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture Wolume 1, Issue , (2021): EJSSPC
9. Международный научно-образовательный электронный журнал «ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НАУКА В XXI ВЕКЕ». Выпуск №18 (том 2) (сентябрь, 2021). Дата выхода в свет: 30.09.2021.
10. Saliyev Sardorbek Alisherovich "Eggplant products grow in uzbekistan in unheated greenhouse appropriate sowing terms and scheme" ISSN 2277-3630 (online), Published by International journal of Social Sciences & Interdisciplinary Research., under Volume: 11 Issue: 01 in January-2022
11. Saliev Sardorbek Alisherovich, Yunusov Oybek Baxodirjonovich (Andijan, Uzbekistan) Productivity and economic efficiency in growing samples of eggplant varieties in an unheated greenhouse in uzbekistan . modern scientific challenges and trends: a collection scientific works of the International scientific conference (7-9 February, 2022) - Warsaw: Sp. z o. o. "iScience", 2022. - 135 p
12. Saliev Sardorbek Alisherovich "The effect of planting terms on growth of eggplant growth in greenhouse conditions" "Экономика и социум" №5(96) 2022

Интернет сайтлари:

<http://www.floraprice.ru>

[https://www./cyberleninka.ru](https://www.cyberleninka.ru)